

Search Engine Ethics and You: Co-Designing Tools for Public Engagement

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1. Overview of the 90-minute workshop session

This workshop invites researchers, practitioners and activists working on search engines and related areas to collaboratively contribute to the development of two new public-facing tools:

1. ***The Ethical Interface*** – a browser extension that offers users real-time prompts and contextual information to support ethical reflection during everyday search activity.
2. ***SEED (Search Engine Encyclopaedia and Database)*** – an open-access platform that distils academic research on search engine ethics into concise, accessible entries for general audiences.

The aim of this session is to bring together scholars and practitioners who are interested in broadening the impact of their work by engaging non-specialist users—such as educators, students, journalists, and civil society organisations—with the ethical issues raised by search technologies.

Search engines are central to how people access information, form opinions, and navigate public discourse. While extensive academic work has addressed issues relating to search engines such as algorithmic bias, fake news, the social impact of search engines on politics and elections, there remains a need to translate this knowledge into forms that are usable, relevant, and engaging for wider audiences. This session builds on that shared concern and seeks to facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration in designing tools that can support public understanding and critical reflection.

2. Workshop structure (90 minutes)

1. ***Introduction and Context (10 minutes)***
A brief overview of the *Search Engine Ethics and You* project, including the rationale behind the development of *The Ethical Interface* and *SEED*. This opening will highlight the tools' intended public-facing role and their potential contribution to digital literacy and critical engagement.
2. ***Demonstration and Walkthrough (15 minutes)***
A short live demonstration of the current prototypes, followed by an outline of their conceptual design. Participants will be introduced to the underlying structure of the tools, the kinds of interactions envisioned, and the strategies used to translate academic material into public resources.

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3. ***Small Group Work: Feedback and Co-Design (30 minutes)***

Participants will divide into groups to examine one of the tools more closely. Through guided prompts, each group will reflect on content structure, usability, tone, accessibility, and potential applications in public or educational contexts. Groups will be invited to identify gaps, suggest content topics, or propose use cases that would make the tools more effective and inclusive.

4. ***Group Reflections and Discussion (20 minutes)***

Each group will report back on key insights and suggestions. A facilitated discussion will follow, aiming to synthesise contributions and identify shared priorities for future development and collaboration.

5. ***Next Steps and Involvement (15 minutes)***

The session will close with a full-group discussion on how participants might remain involved—through contributing to *SEED*, supporting pilot uses of *The Ethical Interface*, or helping shape a broader public engagement strategy. Opportunities for future collaborations, dissemination, and evaluation will also be explored.

3. Outcomes

Participants will:

- Contribute to the development of two tools designed to support public engagement with search engine ethics.
- Share expertise and approaches for translating academic work into accessible public resources.
- Identify opportunities for future collaboration and knowledge exchange, and have the chance to continue contributing to the project.
- Help shape a shared infrastructure for broader ethical engagement with everyday digital technologies and continue to have access to *The Ethical Interface* prototype.

This session offers a space to collaboratively explore how academic expertise in search engine ethics can inform and support wider public understanding, and how tools can be designed to make that knowledge actionable in everyday contexts.